

Joint Exclusivity

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Abstract

We introduce joint exclusivity (JE), a form of extremal negative dependence that extends the classical notion of mutual exclusivity. The JE structure is analytically tractable and is defined by the exclusion of the interior of the non-negative orthant. We establish a sharp necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a JE random vector with prescribed marginals, namely $\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq n - 1$.

We propose a canonical construction that distributes probability mass on lower-dimensional faces of the support, while allowing flexible copula specifications within each face. The framework is further extended to a generalized class (G-JE) via marginal distortion functions. Finally, we identify a correspondence between the support structures of JE and joint mixability, revealing a structural link between the two concepts.

Key words and phrases: counter-monotonicity; joint exclusivity; generalized joint exclusivity; mutual exclusivity; joint mixability

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1 Introduction

Dependence modelling fundamentally relies on selecting structures that adequately capture the phenomenon of interest. Of particular importance are those of extremal nature (Cheung et al., 2014; Deelstra et al., 2011; Dhaene, Denuit, Goovaerts, et al., 2002; Lauzier et al., 2023). In the bivariate setting, the positive extreme is *co-monotonicity* (Dhaene, Denuit, Goovaerts, et al., 2002; Nelsen, 2010), which corresponds to the case where the components move in the same direction. Formally, $X_{12} = (X_1, X_2)$ is co-monotonic if

$$X_{12} \stackrel{d}{=} (h_1(Z), h_2(Z)),$$

for some random variable Z and functions h_1, h_2 that are both non-decreasing (or both non-increasing). This structure is characterised by the Fréchet upper bound

$$F_{12}(x_1, x_2) = \min\{F_1(x_1), F_2(x_2)\},$$

where F_{12} denotes the joint cumulative distribution function (CDF) of X_{12} and F_1, F_2 are the marginal distributions. It represents the strongest form of positive dependence, in the sense that an increase in one component almost surely does not decrease the other.

At the opposite extreme lies *counter-monotonicity* (Dhaene & Denuit, 1999; Nelsen, 2010), where an increase in one component almost surely does not increase the other. Formally, X_{12} is counter-monotonic if

$$X_{12} \stackrel{d}{=} (h_1(Z), h_2(Z)),$$

where h_1 is non-decreasing and h_2 is non-increasing (or vice versa), for some random variable Z . Its joint distribution is given by the Fréchet lower bound

$$F_{12}(x_1, x_2) = \max\{F_1(x_1) + F_2(x_2) - 1, 0\}.$$

In the bivariate case, both Fréchet bounds define valid joint CDFs for arbitrary marginals, F_1 and F_2 , and therefore the two extremal structures are uniquely defined.

These two notions, however, behave differently in higher dimensions. Let $N = \{1, \dots, n\}$ denote the index set. Co-monotonicity extends naturally for $X_N = (X_1, \dots, X_n)$: the representation

$$X_N \stackrel{d}{=} (h_1(Z), \dots, h_n(Z)),$$

where all h_i are non-decreasing (or all non-increasing), remains well-defined for any $n \geq 2$. Moreover, the Fréchet upper bound

$$F_N(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \min_{i \in N} F_i(x_i)$$

is a valid joint distribution for arbitrary marginals and any $n \geq 2$.

In contrast, counter-monotonicity does not admit a canonical multivariate extension. For $n \geq 3$, the stochastic representation is no longer unique, as opposing monotonicity cannot be consistently imposed across more than two components. Correspondingly, the Fréchet lower bound

$$F_N(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \max \left\{ \sum_{i \in N} F_i(x_i) - (n - 1), 0 \right\}$$

fails, in general, to define a valid joint distribution when $n \geq 3$. As a result, several extensions of counter-monotonicity have been proposed, each tailored to specific contexts.

Among the strongest of these is *mutual exclusivity* (ME) (Cheung & Lo, 2014; Dhaene & Denuit, 1999). Let \bar{F} denote the decumulative distribution function (DDF), then a non-negative random vector X_N is said to be ME if

$$\bar{F}_{ij}(0, 0) = 0, \quad \text{for all } i < j, \quad i, j \in N, \tag{1.1}$$

that is, no two components are simultaneously positive. An ME random vector with prescribed marginals F_1, \dots, F_n exists if and only if

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq 1. \tag{1.2}$$

Whenever (1.2) holds, the Fréchet lower bound is a valid joint distribution and coincides with that of the ME random vector. However, condition (1.2) is rather restrictive, which limits the practical applicability of ME.

Alternative notions of counter-monotonicity have been introduced to overcome this limitation, including joint mixability (Wang & Wang, 2016), d -counter-monotonicity (Lee & Ahn, 2014), and Σ -counter-monotonicity; see Puccetti and Wang, 2015 for a unified treatment. These approaches typically impose that a given function of the components is almost surely constant. Although they allow for greater flexibility in the choice of marginals than ME, they are often difficult to construct explicitly or characterise completely for a given set of marginals. This stands in contrast to ME, whose existence is completely determined by condition (1.2) and its construction is exactly the Fréchet lower bound. This motivates the following question: *does there exist a notion of counter-monotonicity that is more flexible than ME, yet remains easy to construct and admits a complete and tractable characterisation analogous to (1.2)?*

A natural answer emerges by relaxing the pairwise requirement in (1.1). Instead of prohibiting any pair of components from being simultaneously positive, one may only require that all n components are never simultaneously positive. This leads to the following definition.

Definition 1.1. *A non-negative random vector X_N is said to be jointly exclusive (JE) if*

$$\bar{F}_N(0, \dots, 0) = 0, \tag{1.3}$$

that is, its support is contained in $[0, \infty)^n \setminus (0, \infty)^n$.

Figure 1: Comparison of the supports of the ME and the JE random vectors for $n = 3$.

When $n = 2$, conditions (1.1) and (1.3) coincide, and thus ME and JE are equivalent. For $n \geq 3$, ME implies JE, but not conversely, making JE a strictly more flexible notion as illustrated in Figure 1. As we demonstrate in this paper, JE additionally admits a canonical construction and a complete characterisation of the admissible marginals, thereby providing an affirmative answer to the question above.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 introduces the notation and presents basic properties of JE. Section 3 develops the main construction methods and characterisation results. Further remarks on the reflected and translated variants of JE as well as its connection to joint mixability are discussed in Section 4. Section 5 concludes.

2 Preliminaries

From the index set $N = \{1, \dots, n\}$ define $M = \{I \subset N : 2 \leq |I| \leq n-1\}$ and for $i \in N$ define the collection $M_i = \{I \in M : i \in I\}$. We primarily consider non-negative random vectors $X_N = (X_1, \dots, X_n)$, with sub-vectors denoted by $X_I = (X_i, i \in I)$ for $I \in M$. Similarly, we

write $x_N = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $x_I = (x_i, i \in I)$ for their deterministic counterparts. We use F , \bar{F} , f , and φ to denote the CDF, DDF, density function, and characteristic function, respectively, with subscripts indicating the corresponding vector or sub-vector. For example, F_N and F_I denote the CDFs of X_N and X_I .

By Definition 1.1 and as illustrated in Figure 1, the support of a JE random vector is singular, lying in an $(n - 1)$ -dimensional subset of \mathbb{R}^n . Consequently, its joint distribution is fully determined by its lower-dimensional margins, as formalized in the following proposition.

Proposition 2.1. *A random vector X_N is JE if and only if its CDF and characteristic function satisfy*

$$F_N(x_N) = \begin{cases} 1 - \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(x_i) + \sum_{I \in M} (-1)^{|I|} \bar{F}_I(x_I), & x_N \in [0, \infty)^n, \\ = (-1)^{n-1} \left(1 - \sum_{i \in N} F_i(x_i) + \sum_{I \in M} (-1)^{|I|} F_I(x_I) \right), & \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

and

$$\varphi_N(t_N) = (-1)^{n-1} \left(1 - \sum_{i \in N} \varphi_i(t_i) + \sum_{I \in M} (-1)^{|I|} \varphi_I(t_I) \right), \quad t_N \in \mathbb{R}^n. \quad (2.2)$$

Proof. The first representation of the CDF follows directly from the inclusion–exclusion principle applied to $F_N(x_N)$, noting that the highest-order term $\bar{F}_N(x_N)$ vanishes under the JE property. The second representation is obtained by applying inclusion–exclusion again to the lower-dimensional terms $\bar{F}_I(x_I)$.

For the characteristic function, observe that

$$\prod_{i \in N} (\exp \{i t_i X_i\} - 1) = 0$$

almost surely due to JE. Taking expectations and expanding the product yields the stated

expression after rearranging terms. □

Remark 2.2. *The CDF representation in (2.1) highlights the structural difference between the JE and the ME dependence. In particular, the higher-order terms*

$$\sum_{I \in \mathcal{M}} (-1)^{|I|} \bar{F}_I(x_I) \tag{2.3}$$

capture interactions beyond the one-dimensional marginals. In the ME case, each term $\bar{F}_I(x_I)$ is zero, so the sum in (2.3) vanishes. Consequently, the CDF reduces to

$$F_N(x_N) = \begin{cases} 1 - \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(x_i) = \sum_{i \in N} F_i(x_i) - (n - 1), & x_N \in [0, \infty)^n, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

which coincides with the Fréchet lower bound. Under condition (1.2), this defines a valid CDF for the ME random vector X_N .

3 Main Results

We begin by establishing the fundamental characterisation of JE random vectors in terms of their marginal distributions.

Theorem 3.1. *Let F_1, \dots, F_n be given marginal distributions. There exists a JE random vector X_N with these marginals if and only if*

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq n - 1. \tag{3.1}$$

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that X_N is JE with marginals F_1, \dots, F_n . By definition 1.1, we

have

$$\bar{F}_N(0, \dots, 0) = 0.$$

Applying the Fréchet lower bound yields

$$\max \left\{ \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - (n - 1), 0 \right\} \leq \bar{F}_N(0, \dots, 0) = 0,$$

which implies $\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq n - 1$.

Sufficiency. Assume that condition (3.1) holds. We construct a JE random vector X_N supported on $[0, \infty)^n \setminus (0, \infty)^n$ by assigning probability masses to its disjoint components.

Step 1: Higher-dimensional faces. For each $I \in M$, define

$$\mathbb{P}(X_i > x_i, i \in I; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus I) = p_I C_I \left(\frac{\bar{F}_i(x_i)}{\bar{F}_i(0)}, i \in I \right), \quad (3.2)$$

for $x_I \in [0, \infty)^{|I|}$, where $p_I \in [0, 1]$ denotes the total probability assigned to the I -th face

$$\{x_N \in [0, \infty)^n \setminus (0, \infty)^n : x_i > 0 \text{ for } i \in I, x_j = 0 \text{ for } j \in N \setminus I\},$$

and C_I are arbitrary copulas (Nelsen, 2010). No consistency between copulas of different dimensions is required i.e. even if $I_1 \subset I_2$ then C_{I_1} is not necessarily a marginal copula of C_{I_2} .

Step 2: Axes. To ensure the correct marginals, for each $i \in N$ we define

$$\mathbb{P}(X_i > x_i; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus \{i\}) = \bar{F}_i(x_i) - \left(\sum_{I \in M_i} p_I \right) \frac{\bar{F}_i(x_i)}{\bar{F}_i(0)}, \quad (3.3)$$

for $x_i \in [0, \infty)$.

Step 3: Origin. Finally, the probability mass at the origin is determined by normalization:

$$\mathbb{P}(X_i = 0, i \in N) = 1 - \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) + \sum_{I \in M} (|I| - 1)p_I. \quad (3.4)$$

The construction yields a valid distribution provided that all assigned masses define proper probabilities. Since (3.2) is valid by construction, it remains to ensure that (3.3) and (3.4) are well-defined.

The non-negativity and monotonicity of (3.3) are equivalent to

$$\sum_{I \in M_i} p_I \leq \bar{F}_i(0), \quad \text{for all } i \in N, \quad (3.5)$$

while (3.4) is non-negative if and only if

$$\sum_{I \in M} (|I| - 1)p_I \geq \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1. \quad (3.6)$$

Thus, the problem reduces to showing that there exist coefficients $p_I \geq 0$ satisfying (3.5)–(3.6).

Step 4: Feasibility via linear programming. Consider the linear program

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} && \sum_{I \in M} (|I| - 1)p_I, && (3.7) \\ & \text{subject to} && p_I \geq 0, && \\ & && \sum_{I \in M_i} p_I \leq \bar{F}_i(0), && i \in N. \end{aligned}$$

Its dual problem is

$$\text{minimize} \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) r_i, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\text{subject to } r_i \geq 0, \quad \sum_{i \in I} r_i \geq |I| - 1, \quad I \in M.$$

By strong duality, the maximum of (3.7) equals the minimum of (3.8). The feasible region of the dual is a polytope, and the minimum is attained at its extreme points. It can be verified that the only relevant vertices are

$$\left(\frac{n-2}{n-1}, \dots, \frac{n-2}{n-1} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad (1, \dots, 1, 0), (1, \dots, 0, 1), \dots, (0, 1, \dots, 1).$$

Evaluating the objective function at these points yields

$$\min \left\{ \frac{n-2}{n-1} \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0), \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - \max_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \right\}. \quad (3.9)$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_{I \in M} (|I| - 1) p_I \leq \min \left\{ \frac{n-2}{n-1} \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0), \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - \max_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \right\}.$$

Combining this with (3.6), existence is ensured if and only if

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1 \leq \min \left\{ \frac{n-2}{n-1} \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0), \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - \max_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \right\}. \quad (3.10)$$

If the minimum is attained by the second term, (3.10) reduces to

$$\max_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq 1,$$

which always holds. If it is attained by the first term, then (3.10) becomes

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq n - 1,$$

which is precisely condition (3.1).

Hence, under (3.1), there exist non-negative coefficients p_I satisfying (3.5)–(3.6), and the construction above defines a valid JE random vector with marginals F_1, \dots, F_n . \square

The necessary and sufficient condition (3.1) for JE is significantly less restrictive than its counterpart (1.2) for ME. This difference becomes increasingly pronounced as the dimension n grows.

Indeed, for JE the condition (3.1) is equivalent to

$$\sum_{i \in N} F_i(0) \geq 1,$$

whereas for ME one requires

$$\sum_{i \in N} F_i(0) \geq n - 1.$$

Consequently, JE allows for substantially greater flexibility in the marginal distributions. In particular, for non-degenerate marginals, it suffices that as few as two of them have atoms at zero, while the remaining $n - 2$ may be fully supported on $(0, \infty)$. In contrast, under ME each marginal must necessarily possess an atom at zero.

To further investigate the structural properties of JE, we adopt the construction introduced in the proof of Theorem 3.1 as a canonical model.

Definition 3.2. X_N is called a canonical JE random vector if its distribution is specified by (3.2)–(3.4), for some coefficients $p_I \in [0, 1]$, $I \in M$, satisfying (3.5)–(3.6).

For fixed marginals, F_1, \dots, F_n , if condition (3.1) holds, then Theorem 3.1 ensures the existence of a canonical JE random vector. Moreover, its CDF admits the following explicit form as a corollary of Proposition 2.1.

Corollary 3.3. *A random vector X_N is a canonical JE random vector if and only if its CDF is given by*

$$F_N(x_N) = \begin{cases} 1 - \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(x_i) + \sum_{I \in M} (-1)^{|I|} \sum_{\substack{J \in M \\ I \subseteq J}} p_J C_J \left(\frac{\bar{F}_i(x_i)}{\bar{F}_i(0)}, i \in I; 1, j \in J \setminus I \right), & x_N \in [0, \infty)^n, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.11)$$

For canonical JE random vectors, the coefficients p_I determine how probability mass is allocated across the different faces of the support, and hence indirectly along the axes and at the origin. Their feasible values are governed entirely by the marginal quantities $\bar{F}_1(0), \dots, \bar{F}_n(0)$. In contrast, the copulas C_I control how the mass p_I is distributed within each face. These copulas can be chosen independently across different I and are not constrained by the marginals.

The following remark highlights several instructive choices of the parameters p_I and their implications for the resulting dependence structure.

Remark 3.4.

(1) *If $p_I = 0$ for some $I \in M$, then the corresponding face is excluded from the support.*

Moreover, by the lower Fréchet bound applied to (3.2),

$$\max \left\{ \sum_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0) + \sum_{j \in N \setminus I} (1 - \bar{F}_j(0)) - (n - 1), 0 \right\} \leq p_I = 0,$$

which implies

$$\sum_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{j \in N \setminus I} \bar{F}_j(0) \leq n - 1 - |N \setminus I|.$$

At the extreme, if $p_I = 0$ for all $I \in M$, then all mass is concentrated on the axes and the

origin, recovering the ME structure. In this case, (3.6) reduces to

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq 1,$$

which is the ME condition (1.2).

- (2) If $p_I = 1$ for some $I \in M$, then all mass is concentrated on the corresponding I -th face, and necessarily $p_J = 0$ for all $J \in M \setminus \{I\}$. From the Fréchet upper bound of (3.2),

$$1 = p_I \leq \min \left\{ \min_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0), \min_{j \in N \setminus I} (1 - \bar{F}_j(0)) \right\},$$

which implies $\bar{F}_i(0) = 1$ for all $i \in I$ and $\bar{F}_j(0) = 0$ for all $j \in N \setminus I$.

- (3) The mass on the i -th axis is determined by (3.3). If no mass is assigned to that axis, then (3.5) must hold with equality:

$$\sum_{I \in M_i} p_I = \bar{F}_i(0).$$

If all axes carry no mass, this yields a system of n linear equations in $|M| = 2^n - n - 2$ unknowns. For $n \geq 4$, the system is under-determined and admits infinitely many solutions. When $n = 3$, the system is exactly determined, leading to the explicit solutions for all $I \in M$

$$p_I = \max \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0) - \bar{F}_j(0)}{2}, 0 \right\}, \quad j \in N \setminus I.$$

- (4) The mass at the origin is governed by (3.4). Provided that (3.5) holds, assigning zero mass at the origin requires

$$\sum_{I \in M} (|I| - 1) p_I = \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1,$$

which corresponds to equality in (3.6).

(5) If $\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) = n - 1$, meaning that equality is achieved in condition (3.1), then by summing the equations in (3.3) over all $i \in N$ and setting each $x_i = 0$, we obtain

$$\sum_{i \in N} \mathbb{P}(X_i > 0; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus \{i\}) + \sum_{I \in M} |I| p_I = n - 1.$$

Furthermore, since $|I| \leq n - 1$, and

$$\sum_{I \in M} p_I = 1 - \mathbb{P}(X_i = 0, i \in N) - \sum_{i \in N} \mathbb{P}(X_i > 0; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus \{i\}),$$

it follows that

$$n - 1 \leq n - 1 - (n - 1)\mathbb{P}(X_i = 0, i \in N) - (n - 2) \sum_{i \in N} \mathbb{P}(X_i > 0; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus \{i\}).$$

This implies that each axis probability, $\mathbb{P}(X_i > 0; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus \{i\})$, as well as the origin probability, $\mathbb{P}(X_i = 0, i \in N)$, must be zero. Consequently, the JE structure concentrates its mass entirely on the faces, such that $\sum_{I \in M} p_I = 1$.

Once the marginals are fixed, the admissible choices of the coefficients p_I are precisely those satisfying conditions (3.5)–(3.6). These coefficients exhibit a particularly tractable structure in the trivariate case ($n = 3$).

To elucidate this, consider the linear relations in (3.5)–(3.6). In general, the $n + 1$ corresponding sums of the coefficients p_I are linearly independent. For $n = 3$, however, the sum in (3.6) is equal to one half of the aggregate of the three sums in (3.5). Hence, one constraint becomes redundant, and the system reduces to three independent linear constraints for the three unknowns (see also Remark 3.4-(3)). This yields a uniquely determined affine structure of admissible solutions.

In particular, parametrized by the same scalar, all coefficients p_I can be expressed as linear

interpolations between their extremal values implied by (3.5)–(3.6). Consequently, the feasible set collapses from a three-dimensional region to a one-dimensional family, which substantially simplifies both the analysis and the implementation. The following proposition makes this structure explicit.

Proposition 3.5. *Let $n = 3$ and suppose that condition (3.1) holds. Define, for each $I \in M$,*

$$p_I = \lambda \min_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0) + (1 - \lambda) \max \left\{ \sum_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1, 0 \right\}. \quad (3.12)$$

Then there exists $\lambda^ \in [0, 1]$ such that the coefficients p_I satisfy (3.5)–(3.6).*

Proof. Assume that (3.1) holds and define

$$U_I = \min_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0), \quad L_I = \max \left\{ \sum_{i \in I} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1, 0 \right\}.$$

Substituting (3.12) into (3.5)–(3.6), and using the fact that $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, yields the constraint

$$\max \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1 - \sum_{I \in M} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)}, 0 \right\} \leq \lambda \leq \min_{i \in N} \left\{ \frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} \right\}. \quad (3.13)$$

Moreover, since $\sum_{I \in M_i} U_I \geq \bar{F}_i(0)$ for at least two indices $i \in N$, the upper bound is at most

1. The inequality $U_I \geq L_I$ follows directly from the Fréchet bounds.

We now show that the interval in (3.13) is non-empty. For each $i \in N$, consider

$$\frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)}.$$

First, note that the numerator can only take one of the following values: $\bar{F}_i(0)$, $1 - \bar{F}_j(0)$ for all $j \in N \setminus \{i\}$, or $2 - \sum_{j \in N} \bar{F}_j(0)$. Each of these quantities is non-negative; in particular,

the non-negativity of the last expression follows from condition (3.1). Hence,

$$\frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} \geq 0.$$

Next, since $\sum_{I \in M} L_I = \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I + L_{N \setminus \{i\}}$, and using the inequality $\sum_{j \in N \setminus \{i\}} \bar{F}_j(0) - 1 - L_{N \setminus \{i\}} \leq 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} &\geq \frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)} \\ &\geq \frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I + \sum_{j \in N \setminus \{i\}} \bar{F}_j(0) - 1 - L_{N \setminus \{i\}}}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)} \\ &= \frac{\sum_{j \in N} \bar{F}_j(0) - 1 - \sum_{I \in M} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)}. \end{aligned}$$

Combining the above bounds yields

$$\frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} \geq \max \left\{ \frac{\sum_{j \in N} \bar{F}_j(0) - 1 - \sum_{I \in M} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)}, 0 \right\},$$

for all $i \in N$. Therefore, the lower bound in (3.13) does not exceed the upper bound, and the interval is non-empty. Consequently, there exists $\lambda^* \in [0, 1]$ such that the coefficients p_I satisfy (3.5)–(3.6). \square

Example 3.6. Let $n = 3$, so that $M = \{\{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}\}$. Suppose $\bar{F}_i(x_i) = (1/2)(1 - x_i)$ for $x_i \in [0, 1]$, $i \in N$. Then $\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) = 3/2$, so condition (3.1) is satisfied.

Using the method in Proposition 3.5, the coefficients are given by

$$p_I = \frac{\lambda}{2}, \quad \lambda \in \left[\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2} \right].$$

At $\lambda = 1/3$, the mass at the origin vanishes (see Remark 3.4-(4)), whereas at $\lambda = 1/2$ the axes carry no mass (see Remark 3.4-(3)). Intermediate values of λ distribute mass across both

components.

Now choose the copulas

$$C_{12}(u_1, u_2) = u_1 u_2, \quad C_{13}(u_1, u_3) = \min\{u_1, u_3\}, \quad C_{23}(u_2, u_3) = \max\{u_2 + u_3 - 1, 0\}.$$

Thus, each face exhibits a distinct dependence structure: independence, co-monotonicity, and counter-monotonicity, respectively.

By Corollary 3.3, the resulting CDF is

$$F_N(x_N) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in N} (1 - x_i) + \frac{\lambda}{2} (1 - x_1)(1 - x_2) \\ \quad + \frac{\lambda}{2} \min\{1 - x_1, 1 - x_3\} + \frac{\lambda}{2} \max\{1 - x_2 - x_3, 0\}, & x_N \in [0, 1]^3, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The support of X_N is illustrated in Figure 2.

Support of canonical JE X_N

Figure 2: Support of the canonical JE random vector X_N with copulas C_{12} , C_{13} , and C_{23} .

The corresponding Pearson correlations are

$$\rho_{12} = \frac{6\lambda - 3}{5}, \quad \rho_{13} = \frac{8\lambda - 3}{5}, \quad \rho_{23} = \frac{4\lambda - 3}{5}.$$

For example,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda = \frac{1}{3} : & \quad \rho_{12} = -\frac{1}{5}, \quad \rho_{13} = -\frac{1}{15}, \quad \rho_{23} = -\frac{1}{3}, \\ \lambda = \frac{5}{12} : & \quad \rho_{12} = -\frac{1}{10}, \quad \rho_{13} = \frac{1}{15}, \quad \rho_{23} = -\frac{4}{15}, \\ \lambda = \frac{1}{2} : & \quad \rho_{12} = 0, \quad \rho_{13} = \frac{1}{5}, \quad \rho_{23} = -\frac{1}{5}. \end{aligned}$$

As λ increases, the correlations tend to increase, reflecting the diminishing influence of mass concentrated on the axes (which induces strong negative dependence). At $\lambda = 1/2$, the dependence is entirely governed by the copulas on the faces.

This example highlights the flexibility of the canonical JE framework. Although the global structure enforces a form of counter-monotonicity, the model accommodates a wide range of local dependence behaviors through the joint specification of the copulas C_I and their coefficients p_I .

Although the canonical JE covers a wide range of modelling choices, its support on the faces is partly governed by the fixed marginals. The copulas C_I may be chosen freely, but the induced joint distribution still inherits the range of the marginals through $\bar{F}_i(x_i)/\bar{F}_i(0)$. To accommodate a broader class of dependence structures on the faces, we introduce a new construction, which we call the *generalized JE* or G-JE, that affords greater control over the probability mass assigned to each face.

Definition 3.7. For each $i \in N$, let $G_i : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a non-decreasing, left-continuous function satisfying $G_i(u) = 0$ for all $u \in [0, a_i]$ and $G_i(u) = 1$ for all $u \in [b_i, 1]$, where $0 \leq a_i < b_i \leq \bar{F}_i(0)$. A random vector X_N is said to be G-JE if its face probabilities are given,

analogously to (3.2)–(3.4), by: for each $I \in M$,

$$\mathbb{P}(X_i > x_i, i \in I; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus I) = p_I C_I(G_i(\bar{F}_i(x_i)), i \in I), \quad x_i \in [0, \infty)^{|I|}; \quad (3.14)$$

for all $i \in N$,

$$\mathbb{P}(X_i > x_i; X_j = 0, j \in N \setminus \{i\}) = \bar{F}_i(x_i) - \left(\sum_{I \in M_i} p_I \right) G_i(\bar{F}_i(x_i)), \quad x_i \in [0, \infty); \quad (3.15)$$

and the probability at the origin is as in (3.4). The coefficients p_I satisfy condition (3.6) as well as

$$\sum_{I \in M_i} p_I \leq G_i^*, \quad \text{for all } i \in N, \quad (3.16)$$

where

$$G_i^* = \inf_{0 \leq x_i < y_i} \frac{\bar{F}_i(x_i) - \bar{F}_i(y_i)}{G_i(\bar{F}_i(x_i)) - G_i(\bar{F}_i(y_i))}. \quad (3.17)$$

Theorem 3.8. *Suppose F_1, \dots, F_n are given marginal distributions. Then a G -JE random vector X_N with these marginals exists if and only if*

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1 \leq \min \left\{ \frac{n-2}{n-1} \sum_{i \in N} G_i^*, \sum_{i \in N} G_i^* - \max_{i \in N} G_i^* \right\}. \quad (3.18)$$

Proof. The proof parallels the sufficiency argument of Theorem 3.1.

Since each G_i is non-decreasing and left-continuous with the prescribed boundary conditions, the compositions $G_i \circ \bar{F}_i$ are well-defined DDFs. By construction, the face probabilities in (3.14) are well-defined; (3.15) is derived so as to recover the prescribed marginals; and the probability at the origin follows by normalization. The non-increasing requirement on (3.15) yields condition (3.16) with the constants defined in (3.17), while non-negativity of the origin probability is equivalent to (3.6). Finally, applying the same linear programming machinery as

in (3.7)–(3.8), with G_i^* in place of $\bar{F}_i(0)$, gives the bound

$$\min \left\{ \frac{n-2}{n-1} \sum_{i \in N} G_i^*, \sum_{i \in N} G_i^* - \max_{i \in N} G_i^* \right\},$$

so existence is guaranteed if and only if (3.18) holds. \square

Remark 3.9.

- (1) *The G-JE is strictly more flexible than the canonical JE: the constants a_i and b_i restrict the support on each face to a sub-range, while the functions G_i introduce distortions within that range, all without disrupting the overall JE structure. The price paid is a more stringent existence condition (3.18) compared to (3.1). Indeed, evaluating G_i^* at $x_i = 0$ and $y_i \rightarrow \infty$ gives*

$$0 \leq G_i^* \leq \frac{\bar{F}_i(0) - \bar{F}_i(\infty)}{G_i(\bar{F}_i(0)) - G_i(\bar{F}_i(\infty))} = \bar{F}_i(0),$$

so $G_i^* \leq \bar{F}_i(0)$ always, making (3.16) more restrictive than (3.5) and the admissible set for the parameters p_I correspondingly smaller. When \bar{F}_i attains the values a_i and b_i , this bound sharpens to

$$0 \leq G_i^* \leq \frac{b_i - a_i}{G_i(b_i) - G_i(a_i)} = b_i - a_i \leq \bar{F}_i(0).$$

- (2) *If \bar{F}_i is continuous at some point x_i^* while $G_i \circ \bar{F}_i$ has a jump there, then along any sequence $x_i^{(k)} \nearrow x_i^*$ we have $\bar{F}_i(x_i^{(k)}) - \bar{F}_i(x_i^*) \rightarrow 0$ while $G_i(\bar{F}_i(x_i^{(k)})) - G_i(\bar{F}_i(x_i^*)) \rightarrow c > 0$, forcing $G_i^* = 0$. Condition (3.16) then requires*

$$p_I = 0 \quad \text{for all } I \in M_i.$$

This is to be expected: if $p_I > 0$ for some $I \in M_i$, then the mass at x_i^* on the I -th face would force a jump in \bar{F}_i at that point, contradicting the assumed continuity. Thus, to avoid degeneracy, wherever \bar{F}_i is continuous, $G_i \circ \bar{F}_i$ must be continuous as well.

- (3) If $G_i \circ \bar{F}_i$ is constant on some sub-interval while \bar{F}_i is strictly increasing there, the ratio in (3.17) diverges. This causes no difficulty, as the infimum simply disregards such pairs.
- (4) The CDF of a G-JE random vector X_N takes the same form as the canonical expression (3.11), with each argument $\bar{F}_i(x_i)/\bar{F}_i(0)$ of the copula C_J replaced by $G_i(\bar{F}_i(x_i))$.
- (5) The result in Remark 3.4-(1) carries over to G-JE without modification. Item (2) of that remark holds with the additional constraint $G_i^* = \bar{F}_i(0) = 1$ for all $i \in I$. Analogously to Remark 3.4-(3), no mass is assigned to the i -th axis whenever

$$\sum_{I \in M_i} p_I = G_i^*,$$

and in this case we necessarily have $G_i(\bar{F}_i(x_i)) = \bar{F}_i(x_i)/\bar{F}_i(0)$, thus $G_i^* = \bar{F}_i(0)$. For $n = 3$, if all axes carry zero probability, then each p_I can be written explicitly and uniquely. Item (4) of that remark holds without modification while the implication in item (5) does not generally extend to G-JE random vectors.

Analogously to Proposition 3.5, any trivariate G-JE random vector admits a convenient one-parameter linear interpolation representation for the coefficients p_I , as stated below.

Proposition 3.10. *Suppose condition (3.18) holds for a trivariate set of marginals. Define, for each $I \in M$,*

$$p_I = \lambda \min_{i \in I} G_i^* + (1 - \lambda) \max \left\{ \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - G_j^* - 1, 0 \right\}, \quad j \in N \setminus I. \quad (3.19)$$

Then there exists $\lambda^* \in [0, 1]$ such that the coefficients p_I satisfy both (3.16) and (3.6).

Proof. The proof mirrors that of Proposition 3.5. Assume (3.18) holds and set

$$U_I = \min_{i \in I} G_i^*, \quad L_I = \max \left\{ \sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - G_j^* - 1, 0 \right\}, \quad j \in N \setminus I.$$

Substituting (3.19) into (3.16) and (3.6), and using $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, yields the constraint

$$\max \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1 - \sum_{I \in M} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)}, 0 \right\} \leq \lambda \leq \min_{i \in N} \left\{ \frac{G_i^* - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} \right\}. \quad (3.20)$$

Since $\sum_{I \in M_i} U_I \geq G_i^*$ for at least two indices $i \in N$, the upper bound does not exceed 1. Moreover, (3.18) ensures $U_I \geq L_I$ for all $I \in M$, so the denominators are positive.

It remains to show that the interval in (3.20) is non-empty. Fix $i \in N$. The numerator of the i -th term in the upper bound equals one of the following quantities: G_i^* ; $G_i^* + G_j^* - (\sum_{k \in N} \bar{F}_k(0) - 1)$ for $j \in N \setminus \{i\}$; or $\sum_{k \in N} G_k^* - 2(\sum_{k \in N} \bar{F}_k(0) - 1)$. All three are non-negative by condition (3.18), so

$$\frac{G_i^* - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} \geq 0.$$

Furthermore, using $\sum_{I \in M} L_I = \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I + L_{N \setminus \{i\}}$ together with $\sum_{k \in N} \bar{F}_k(0) - G_i^* - 1 - L_{N \setminus \{i\}} \leq 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{G_i^* - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} &\geq \frac{G_i^* - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)} \\ &\geq \frac{G_i^* - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I + \sum_{k \in N} \bar{F}_k(0) - G_i^* - 1 - L_{N \setminus \{i\}}}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)} \\ &= \frac{\sum_{k \in N} \bar{F}_k(0) - 1 - \sum_{I \in M} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)}. \end{aligned}$$

Combining both bounds gives

$$\frac{G_i^* - \sum_{I \in M_i} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M_i} (U_I - L_I)} \geq \max \left\{ \frac{\sum_{k \in N} \bar{F}_k(0) - 1 - \sum_{I \in M} L_I}{\sum_{I \in M} (U_I - L_I)}, 0 \right\},$$

so the interval (3.20) is non-empty, and there exists $\lambda^* \in [0, 1]$ such that the coefficients p_I satisfy both (3.16) and (3.6). \square

We close this section with illustrative examples of the functions G_i and the rich G-JE structures they generate.

Example 3.11.

- (1) Consider the linear functions $G_i(u) = \alpha_i u + \beta_i$, with $\alpha_i > 0$ and $\beta_i \in \mathbb{R}$, defined on $[a_i, b_i]$ and extended by $G_i(u) = 0$ for $u \in [0, a_i]$ and $G_i(u) = 1$ for $u \in [b_i, 1]$. The boundary conditions $\alpha_i a_i + \beta_i = 0$ and $\alpha_i b_i + \beta_i = 1$ uniquely determine $\alpha_i = 1/(b_i - a_i)$ and $\beta_i = -a_i/(b_i - a_i)$, giving

$$G_i(u) = \frac{u - a_i}{b_i - a_i}, \quad u \in [a_i, b_i].$$

Setting $a_i = 0$ and $b_i = \bar{F}_i(0)$ recovers the canonical JE, since then $G_i^* = \bar{F}_i(0)$.

Now take $a_i > 0$ and $b_i = \bar{F}_i(0)$, and assume that each \bar{F}_i attains at least one value in $[a_i, \bar{F}_i(0))$. Then $G_i^* = \bar{F}_i(0) - a_i$, and condition (3.18) becomes

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) - 1 \leq \min \left\{ \frac{n-2}{n-1} \sum_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i), \sum_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i) - \max_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i) \right\}.$$

When $\sum_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i) \geq (n-1) \max_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i)$, the first term is the minimum and the condition reduces to

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) + (n-2) \sum_{i \in N} a_i \leq n-1.$$

Compared with (3.1), the extra term $(n-2) \sum_{i \in N} a_i$ reflects the additional restriction

imposed by the distortions G_i . When instead $\sum_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i) \leq (n-1) \max_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i)$, the second term is the minimum and the condition becomes

$$\sum_{i \in N} a_i + \max_{i \in N} (\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i) \leq 1,$$

a constraint that primarily controls the lower bounds a_i . Setting $a_i = 1 - q_i$, the two conditions may be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in N} (1 - q_i) + \frac{\sum_{i \in N} (q_i - F_i(0))}{n-1} &\leq 1, \\ \sum_{i \in N} (1 - q_i) + \max_{i \in N} (q_i - F_i(0)) &\leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

The second inequality is precisely the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of the Tail-ME random vector with probability vector (q_1, \dots, q_n) studied in Cheung et al., 2017. The first inequality additionally ensures that the G-JE variant of the Tail-ME has its body support confined to the lower faces of the box $B = \{x_N \in [0, \infty)^n : 0 \leq x_i \leq F_i^{-1}(q_i)\}$ (where F_i^{-1} denotes the left-inverse of F_i), rather than spread across the full n -cube B .

As a concrete illustration, modify Example 3.6 by replacing $G_i(u) = u/\bar{F}_i(0)$ with $G_i(u) = (u - a_i)/(\bar{F}_i(0) - a_i)$, retaining $\bar{F}_i(0) = 1/2$ and setting $a_i = 1/8$ for all $i \in N$. A direct computation gives $G_i^* = 3/8$, and condition (3.18) is satisfied. Choosing p_I via (3.19)–(3.20) in Proposition 3.10 yields

$$p_I = \frac{3}{8} \lambda + \frac{1}{8} (1 - \lambda), \quad \lambda \in \left[\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{4} \right].$$

The resulting CDF of X_N is

$$F_N(x_N) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in N} (1 - x_i) \\ + \left(\frac{3}{8} \lambda + \frac{1}{8} (1 - \lambda) \right) \left[\max \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{3} x_1, 0 \right\} \max \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{3} x_2, 0 \right\} \right. \\ \quad \left. + \min \left\{ \max \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{3} x_1, 0 \right\}, \max \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{3} x_3, 0 \right\} \right\} \right. \\ \quad \left. + \max \left\{ \max \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{3} x_2, 0 \right\} + \max \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{3} x_3, 0 \right\} - 1, 0 \right\} \right], & x_N \in [0, 1]^3, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The support of X_N is depicted in Figure 3.

Support of G-JE X_N

Figure 3: Support of the G-JE random vector X_N with G_i as linear truncations at 0.75.

(2) Consider the power functions $G_i(u) = (\alpha_i u + \beta_i)^\gamma$, with $\alpha_i > 0$, $\beta_i \in \mathbb{R}$, and a common

exponent $\gamma > 0$. The same boundary conditions as in the linear case force

$$G_i(u) = \left(\frac{u - a_i}{b_i - a_i} \right)^\gamma, \quad u \in [a_i, b_i].$$

If $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ and \bar{F}_i takes values in $(a_i, a_i + \varepsilon)$ for some $\varepsilon > 0$, then $G_i^* = 0$ and all face probabilities vanish. The case $\gamma = 1$ recovers the linear example above. If $\gamma > 1$ and \bar{F}_i takes values in $(b_i - \varepsilon, b_i)$ for some $\varepsilon > 0$, then $G_i^* = (b_i - a_i)/\gamma$. Setting $a_i = 0$ and $b_i = \bar{F}_i(0)$, condition (3.18) becomes

$$\sum_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0) \leq \min \left\{ \frac{\gamma(n-1)}{\gamma(n-1) - (n-2)}, \frac{\gamma - \max_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0)}{\gamma - 1} \right\}.$$

One can verify that the right-hand side does not exceed $n-1$, consistent with the restriction imposed by non-linear distortions. Moreover, for fixed n and $\max_{i \in N} \bar{F}_i(0)$, the bound is decreasing in γ , confirming that larger values of γ impose progressively stronger constraints relative to the canonical JE.

4 Further Discussion

The preceding sections provided a thorough study of the JE structure: we fully characterized its existence, examined its distributional properties, and derived a tractable canonical form, which was subsequently extended to the G-JE via the distortion functions G_i on the marginals.

The primary variant of JE considered throughout this work is *JE from below*, defined by the condition $\bar{F}_N(0, \dots, 0) = 0$ for non-negative random vectors X_N . In a manner analogous to ME, the *JE from above* counterpart is defined by the condition $\mathbb{P}(Y_i < 0, i \in N) = 0$ for non-positive random vectors Y_N .

By symmetry, Y_N is JE from above if and only if $X_N := -Y_N$ is JE from below. Conse-

quently, with appropriate adjustments for reflection, all results established in Sections 2 and 3 extend to the "from above" case. In particular, condition (3.1) is reformulated as:

$$\sum_{i \in N} \mathbb{P}(Y_i < 0) \leq n - 1.$$

Furthermore, any JE from below random vector X_N is closed under component-wise translation. Specifically, for constants $l_i \in \mathbb{R}$, the translated vector $Y_i = X_i + l_i$ remains JE, where condition (3.1) takes the form:

$$\sum_{i \in N} \mathbb{P}(Y_i > l_i) \leq n - 1.$$

An identical translation argument applies to the case of JE from above.

As noted in the introduction, JE is not the only higher-dimensional counter-monotonic structure. Another prominent concept is *joint mixability* (JM). A random vector Y_N is JM if $\sum_{i \in N} Y_i = c$ almost surely for some constant $c \in \mathbb{R}$ (taken without loss of generality to be 0). Although these two notions may appear unrelated, they are intimately connected through the geometry of their supports. Both supports are singular and contained in $(n - 1)$ -dimensional non-increasing subsets of \mathbb{R}^n . The support of JM lies in the hyperplane $\{y_N : \sum_{i \in N} y_i = 0\}$, while that of JE lies in boundary of the non-negative orthant $[0, \infty)^n \setminus (0, \infty)^n$. It is therefore natural to ask whether a bijection exists between the two supports.

Indeed, define $W_{\text{JE}} = \{x_N \in [0, \infty)^n \setminus (0, \infty)^n\}$ and $W_{\text{JM}} = \{y_N \in \mathbb{R}^n : \sum_{i \in N} y_i = 0\}$, and let $\Phi : W_{\text{JE}} \rightarrow W_{\text{JM}}$ be given by

$$\Phi(x_N) = \left(x_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j \in N} x_j, i \in N \right), \quad \text{with inverse} \quad \Phi^{-1}(y_N) = \left(y_i - \min_{j \in N} y_j, i \in N \right).$$

To verify bijectivity, take $x_N \in W_{\text{JE}}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi^{-1}(\Phi(x_N)) &= \left(\left(x_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j \in N} x_j \right) - \min_{k \in N} \left(x_k - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j \in N} x_j \right), i \in N \right) \\ &= \left(x_i - \min_{k \in N} x_k, i \in N \right) = x_N,\end{aligned}$$

where the last equality uses $\min_{k \in N} x_k = 0$. Conversely, for $y_N \in W_{\text{JM}}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(\Phi^{-1}(y_N)) &= \left(\left(y_i - \min_{j \in N} y_j \right) - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k \in N} \left(y_k - \min_{j \in N} y_j \right), i \in N \right) \\ &= \left(y_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k \in N} y_k, i \in N \right) = y_N,\end{aligned}$$

where the last equality uses $\sum_{k \in N} y_k = 0$.

Consequently, if X_N is JE then $Y_N := (X_i - \bar{X}, i \in N)$ is JM, and conversely, if Y_N is JM then $X_N := (Y_i + \bar{X}, i \in N)$ is JE. Figure 4 illustrates the two sets W_{JE} and W_{JM} for $n = 3$.

5 Conclusions

This paper establishes joint exclusivity (JE) as a rigorous and analytically tractable framework for modeling extremal negative dependence in arbitrary dimensions. By relaxing the pairwise constraints inherent in mutual exclusivity, JE resolves key structural rigidities while preserving a geometrically transparent support. We have provided a complete characterization of the existence of JE random vectors, showing that the admissibility condition is substantially less restrictive than that of mutual exclusivity.

Our canonical construction separates global marginal constraints from local dependence, enabling the latter to be specified flexibly through copulas on lower-dimensional faces. This

Supports of JE and JM

Figure 4: The sets W_{JE} and W_{JM} as supports of JE and JM random vectors ($n = 3$).

flexibility is further enhanced by the generalized JE (G-JE) extension via marginal distortion functions, accommodating a broader class of dependence structures. Moreover, by establishing a geometric bijection between the supports of JE and joint mixability, we uncover a unifying structural link between two fundamental paradigms of extremal dependence.

These results, together with the inherent tractability of the JE framework, suggest promising directions for future research, including applications to optimal transport, risk aggregation, and the statistical inference of negatively dependent systems.

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